

First record of *Carybdea marsupialis* (Cnidaria: Cubomedusae), in the southern coast of Sicily (Central Mediterranean)

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Cubozoa (Werner, 1973) is a class of the phylum Cnidaria consist of two orders, the Carybdeida (Péron & Lesueur, 1810) and Chirodropida (Haeckel, 1880) (Gueroun et al., 2015). The *Carybdea marsupialis* (Linnaeus, 1758) is a box jellyfish of the family Carybdeidae (Gegenbaur, 1857) widely distributed in tropical waters of the Atlantic and Pacific Ocean (Bordehore et al., 2011). Notably, this jellyfish is the only cubozoan species reported in the Mediterranean Sea (Acevedo et al., 2019). Cubozoans are organisms with a biphasic life cycle (polyp and free-swimming medusa) and feed on ichthyoplankton and zooplankton organisms (Gueroun et al., 2015). In particular, jellyfishes of the Carybdeidae family are composed by a cuboidal shaped bell, one tentacle for each of the four pedalia and generally occurring in coastal shallow waters (Kazmi & Sultana, 2008). This note reports the first record of *C. marsupialis* in the southern coast of Sicily. On 6th August 2019 and 10th February 2020, box jellyfish was observed near the water surface (Fig. 1A) of two sites distant about 6 nm, namely Giallonardo beach (37°19'16"N, 13°24'52"E; 1 individual) and the harbour of Porto Empedocle (37°17'13"N, 13°31'44"E; up to 3 individuals per square meter), respectively. Further, one individual from both sites was, photographed (Fig. 1B) and identified following Kazmi & Sultana (2008). According to local people, the occurrence of *C. marsupialis* in the harbour of Porto Empedocle lasted two weeks whereas fisher stated that no individuals were never caught. This may suggest that *C. marsupialis* did not found proper environmental conditions for its settlement in the area. In our opinion, its occurrence in both sites may be due either to an accidental release of medusae by ship ballast water discharges or polyps transported by hull fouling of distant trawlers operating off the coasts of north Africa (Falsone et al, 2020) which back to own home port, as in the case of Porto Empedocle fleet. Considering the public concern associated with the painful sting of *C. marsupialis* (Gueroun et al., 2015) and its potential impact to the marine ecosystem due to the predation upon small pelagic larvae (Bordehore et al., 2011), a proliferation of this box jellyfish in the Sicilian coasts could affect negatively both local tourism and fisheries (Gueroun et al., 2015). Hence, further researches and monitoring activities involving local citizens and fishers are recommended.

Keywords: Cubozoa, *Carybdea marsupialis*, box jellyfish, central Mediterranean, new record

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Fig. 1 (A-B). The individual of *Carybdea marsupialis* photographed in the harbour of Porto Empedocle (Fig. 1A) and in a tank (Fig. 2B).

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